

REPRESENTATION OF REAL NUMBERS BY THE ALTERNATING CANTOR SERIES

Symon Serbenyuk

Institute of Mathematics, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine
simon6@ukr.net

Received: 5/14/16, Accepted: 4/6/17, Published: 5/24/17

Abstract

The article is devoted to alternating Cantor series. It is proved that any real number belonging to $[a_0 - 1, a_0]$, where $a_0 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k}-1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}$, has not more than two representations by such series, and only the numbers from a certain countable subset of real numbers have two representations. The geometry of these representations, properties of cylinder and semicylinder sets, and the simplest metric problems are investigated. Some applications of such series to fractal theory and the relation between positive and alternating Cantor series are described. The shift operator with some its applications, as well as the set of incomplete sums are studied. Necessary and sufficient conditions for a rational number to be representable by an alternating Cantor series are formulated.

Introduction

The investigation of various numeral systems is useful for the development of metric, probability, and fractal theories of real numbers, for the study of fractal and other properties of mathematical objects possessing a complicated local structure such as continuous nowhere differentiable or singular functions, random variables of Jessen-Wintner type, DP-transformations (transformations preserving the fractal Hausdorff-Besicovitch dimension), dynamical systems with chaotic trajectories, etc. [2, 3].

There exist systems of real number representations with a finite or an infinite alphabet, with redundant digits or with zero redundancy. The s -adic and nega- s -adic numeral systems [5] are examples of real number encodings with a finite alphabet, whereas number representations by Lüroth series [6], regular continued fractions, polybasic nega- \tilde{Q} -representations [11], etc., are examples of encoding them with an infinite alphabet. A representation

$$x = \frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2} + \cdots + \frac{\varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} + \cdots, \varepsilon_n \in A_{d_n}, \quad (1)$$

of a real number x by a positive Cantor series [1, 7, 8], is an example of a polybasic numeral system with zero redundancy. Here (d_n) is a fixed sequence of positive integers, $d_n > 1$, and (A_{d_n}) is a sequence of the sets $A_{d_n} = \{0, 1, \dots, d_n - 1\}$. This encoding of real numbers has a finite alphabet when (d_n) is bounded.

The representation of real numbers by positive Cantor series is a generalization of the classical s -adic numeral system. Note that this representation is “similar” to the following series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n},$$

where (a_n) is a monotone non-decreasing sequence of positive integers and $a_1 \geq 1$. This series is called an Engel series.

In 1869, Georg Cantor [1] considered series expansions of real numbers (1). There are many papers [1, 4, 7, 10, 8] where properties of real number representations by positive Cantor series are studied, but many problems related to these series are not solved completely. For example, criteria of representation of rational numbers, modeling of functions with a complicated local structure are still open problems.

Since real number expansions by positive Cantor series are useful for studying complicated objects of fractal analysis, the notion of alternating Cantor series is introduced in the present article. Alternating Cantor series, which generalize the nega- s -adic numeral system, were not considered in publications earlier. In this paper the foundations of the metric theory of real number representations by alternating Cantor series are given and some related problems of mathematical analysis are considered.

Consider the main object of this article.

Let (d_n) be a fixed sequence of numbers from $\mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, (A_{d_n}) be a sequence of the sets $A_{d_n} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, d_n - 1\}$.

Definition 1. A series of the form

$$-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2} - \frac{\varepsilon_3}{d_1 d_2 d_3} + \cdots + \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 d_3 \cdots d_n} + \cdots, \tag{2}$$

where $\varepsilon_n \in A_{d_n}$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, is called *an alternating Cantor series*.

The number d_n is called *the n th element* of sum (2), and ε_n is called *the n th digit* of sum (2).

By $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$ denote any number x having expansion (2). This notation is called *the nega- D -representation of x* . Expansion (2) of x is called *the nega- D -expansion of x* .

Remark 1. The term “nega” is used in this article, since the alternating Cantor series expansion is a numeral system with a negative base, i.e.,

$$x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} = \frac{\varepsilon_1}{-d_1} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{(-d_1)(-d_2)} + \cdots + \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(-d_1)(-d_2) \cdots (-d_n)} + \cdots$$

If (d_n) is purely periodic with the simple period (s) , where $s > 1$ is a fixed positive integer, then series (2) has the form

$$x = -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{s} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{s^2} - \frac{\varepsilon_3}{s^3} + \cdots + \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{s^n} + \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{0, 1, \dots, s-1\}.$$

The last-mentioned series is the nega- s -adic expansion [5, 9] of numbers in $[-\frac{s}{s+1}, \frac{1}{s+1}]$.

The following series are alternating Cantor series:

1.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{s^{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \dots + \alpha_n}},$$

where α_n belongs to some finite subset of positive integers, $\varepsilon_n \in \{0, 1, \dots, s^{\alpha_n} - 1\}$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and $1 < s \in \mathbb{N}$ is a fixed number;

2.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot (n+1)}, \varepsilon_n \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\};$$

3.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_n},$$

where (p_n) is the increasing sequence of all prime numbers.

Lemma 1. *Every alternating Cantor series is absolutely convergent and its sum belongs to $[a_0 - 1, a_0]$, where*

$$a_0 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2n} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2n}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n}.$$

Proof. This statement follows from the propositions:

- the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n}$$

is convergent;

- the condition

$$-1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \leq S \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n},$$

holds, where S is equal to the sum of series (2).

□

Lemma 2. *Let series (2) be a fixed series,*

$$r_n = \frac{(-1)^n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k \varepsilon_{n+k}}{d_{n+1} \cdots d_{n+k}}, \text{ and } a_n = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{d_{n+1} d_{n+2} \cdots d_{n+k}}$$

for this series; then the following inequalities hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_n - 1}{d_1 \cdots d_n} \leq r_n \leq \frac{a_n}{d_1 \cdots d_n} \text{ whenever } n \text{ is even;} \\ -\frac{a_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \leq r_n \leq \frac{1 - a_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \text{ whenever } n \text{ is odd.} \end{aligned}$$

1. Representation of Real Numbers by Alternating Cantor Series

Lemma 3. *Each number $x \in [a_0 - 1, a_0]$ can be represented by series (2).*

Proof. It is obvious that $a_0 - 1 = \Delta_{[d_1-1]0[d_3-1]0\dots}^{-D}$ and $a_0 = \Delta_{0[d_2-1]0[d_4-1]\dots}^{-D}$.
 Since x is an arbitrary number from $(a_0 - 1, a_0)$,

$$-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}} < x \leq -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}$$

with $0 \leq \varepsilon_1 \leq d_1 - 1$, and

$$[a_0 - 1, a_0] = I_0 = \bigcup_{i=0}^{d_1-1} \left[-\frac{i}{d_1} - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}}, -\frac{i}{d_1} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}} \right],$$

we have

$$-\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}} < x + \frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}.$$

Let $x + \frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} = x_1$. Then we obtain the following cases:

1. If the equality

$$x_1 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}$$

holds, then

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1[d_2-1]0[d_4-1]0\dots}^{-D} \text{ or } x = \Delta_{[\varepsilon_1-1]0[d_3-1]0[d_5-1]0\dots}^{-D}.$$

2. If the first case does not hold, then $x = -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + x_1$, where

$$\frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2} - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}} \leq x_1 < \frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2} + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}.$$

In this case, let $x_2 = x_1 - \frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2}$. Then:

1. if the equality

$$x_2 = \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}}$$

holds, then

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 [d_3-1]0[d_5-1]0\dots}^{-D} \text{ or } x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 [\varepsilon_2-1]0[d_4-1]0[d_6-1]0\dots}^{-D}$$

2. In the converse case,

$$x = -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2} + x_2, \text{ where}$$

$$-\frac{\varepsilon_3}{d_1 d_2 d_3} - \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}} < x_2 \leq -\frac{\varepsilon_3}{d_1 d_2 d_3} + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}, \text{ etc.}$$

Therefore,

$$-\sum_{k > \frac{m+2}{2}} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}} < x_m - \frac{(-1)^{m+1} \varepsilon_{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{m+1}} < \sum_{k > \frac{m+1}{2}} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}}$$

for some positive integer m . Moreover, the following cases are possible:

- 1.

$$x_{m+1} = \begin{cases} \sum_{k > \frac{m+2}{2}} \frac{d_{2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd} \\ \sum_{k > \frac{m+1}{2}} \frac{d_{2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}} & \text{if } m \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

In this case,

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m+1} [d_{m+2}-1]0[d_{m+4}-1]0\dots}^{-D}$$

or

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_m [\varepsilon_{m+1}-1]0[d_{m+3}-1]0[d_{m+5}-1]0\dots}^{-D}$$

2. If there does not exist a number $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the last-mentioned system is satisfied, then

$$x = -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + x_1 = \dots = -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{d_1 d_2} - \frac{\varepsilon_3}{d_1 d_2 d_3} + \dots + \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} + x_n = \dots$$

Hence,

$$x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n}.$$

□

Lemma 4. *The numbers*

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m-1} \varepsilon_m \varepsilon_{m+1} \dots}^{-D} \quad \text{and} \quad x' = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m-1} \varepsilon'_m \varepsilon'_{m+1} \dots}^{-D}$$

where $\varepsilon_m \neq \varepsilon'_m$, are equal if and only if one of the following systems

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \varepsilon_{m+2i-1} = d_{m+2i-1} - 1 \\ \varepsilon_{m+2i} = 0 \\ \varepsilon'_{m+2i} = d_{m+2i} - 1 \\ \varepsilon_m = \varepsilon_m - 1 \end{array} \right. = \varepsilon'_{m+2i-1} \quad \text{or} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \varepsilon_{m+2i} = d_{m+2i} - 1 \\ \varepsilon_{m+2i-1} = 0 \\ \varepsilon'_{m+2i-1} = d_{m+2i-1} - 1 \\ \varepsilon_m - 1 = \varepsilon_m \end{array} \right.$$

is satisfied for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. We prove necessity. Let $\varepsilon_m = \varepsilon'_m + 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= x - x' = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m-1} \varepsilon_m \varepsilon_{m+1} \dots}^{-D} - \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m-1} \varepsilon'_m \varepsilon'_{m+1} \dots}^{-D} = \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} \\ &+ \frac{(-1)^{m+1}(\varepsilon_{m+1} - \varepsilon'_{m+1})}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} + \dots + \frac{\varepsilon_{m+i} - \varepsilon'_{m+i}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+i}} (-1)^{m+i} + \dots \\ &= \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} \left(1 + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i (\varepsilon_{m+i} - \varepsilon'_{m+i})}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \dots d_{m+i}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i (\varepsilon_{m+i} - \varepsilon'_{m+i})}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \dots d_{m+i}} \geq - \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+i} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \dots d_{m+i}} = -1.$$

The last-mentioned inequality is an equality when

$$\varepsilon_{m+2i} = \varepsilon'_{m+2i-1} = 0, \quad \varepsilon_{m+2i-1} = d_{m+2i-1} - 1, \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon'_{m+2i} = d_{m+2i} - 1.$$

In our case, the conditions of the first system follow from $x = x'$. It is easy to see that the conditions of the second system follow from $x = x'$ when $\varepsilon'_m = \varepsilon_m + 1$.

The proof of *sufficiency* is trivial. □

Definition 2. The nega-D-representation $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$ of some number $x \in [a_0 - 1, a_0]$ is called *periodic* if there exist numbers $m \in \mathbb{Z}_0$ and $t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the equality $\varepsilon_{m+nt+j} = \varepsilon_{m+j}$ holds for each $n \in \mathbb{N}, j \in \mathbb{N}$.

Denote by $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m (\varepsilon_{m+1} \varepsilon_{m+2} \dots \varepsilon_{m+t})}^{-D}$ any number whose nega-D-representation is periodic with *the period* $(\varepsilon_{m+1} \varepsilon_{m+2} \dots \varepsilon_{m+t})$ of *length* t .

A periodic representation is:

- *purely periodic* if $m = 0$;
- *mixed periodic* if $m > 0$.

Definition 3. Denote by

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m \phi_1(d_{m+1}) \phi_2(d_{m+2}) \dots \phi_t(d_{m+t}) \phi_1(d_{m+t+1}) \phi_2(d_{m+t+2}) \dots \phi_t(d_{m+2t}) \dots}$$

any quasi-periodic number x . Here $m \in \mathbb{Z}_0$, $t \in \mathbb{N}$, and $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_t$ are functions such that $\phi_i(d_n) \in A_{d_n}$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $i = \overline{1, t}$. That is $\phi_i(d_n)$ is a regularity that depends on the parameter d_n .

The following numbers are quasi-periodic:

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n 0[d_{n+2}-1][d_{n+3}-1] \dots [d_{n+i}-1] \dots}, \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n 0[d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0[d_{n+5}-1] \dots}, \text{ etc.}$$

Definition 4. A number $x \in I_0 = [a_0 - 1, a_0]$ is called *nega-D-rational* if

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} \varepsilon_n [d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0[d_{n+5}-1] \dots}$$

or

$$x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} [\varepsilon_n - 1]0[d_{n+2}-1]0[d_{n+4}-1]0[d_{n+6}-1] \dots}$$

The other numbers in I_0 are called *nega-D-irrational*.

The next proposition follows from Lemma 3 and Lemma 4.

Theorem 1. Every *nega-D-irrational* number has the unique *nega-D-representation*. Every *nega-D-rational* number has two *nega-D-representations*, i.e.,

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} \varepsilon_n [d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0[d_{n+5}-1] \dots} = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} [\varepsilon_n - 1]0[d_{n+2}-1]0[d_{n+4}-1]0[d_{n+6}-1] \dots}$$

Remark 2. There exist sequences (d_n) such that a *nega-D-rational* number is an irrational number. For example, the following numbers are *nega-D-rational*:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \frac{(-1)^n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \left(-1 - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot (j+1)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \frac{(-1)^n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \left(-1 + \frac{1}{e} \right), \\ x &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \frac{(-1)^n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \left(-1 - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot \dots \cdot 2j} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{e}}{e}, \end{aligned}$$

since

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_n [d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0 \dots} = g_n + \frac{(-1)^n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \left(-1 - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j}{d_{n+1} \dots d_{n+j}} \right)$$

and

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} [\varepsilon_n - 1] 0 [d_{n+2} - 1] 0 \dots}^{-D} = g_n + \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j}{d_{n+1} \dots d_{n+j}} \right),$$

where

$$g_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i}.$$

To avoid some inconveniences in the future, we can modify expansion (2) of $x \in [-1 + a_0, a_0]$ to the following form

$$x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 + \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} (-1)^{n+1}, \tag{3}$$

where x represented in form (3) belongs to $[0, 1]$, $\varepsilon_n \in A_{d_n}$, and $a_0 = -\Delta_{(1)}^{-D}$.

It is easy to see that

$$\inf \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \right) = g' - \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2i} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2i}} = 0$$

and

$$\sup \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \right) = g' + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2i-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2i-1}} = 1,$$

where

$$g' = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n}.$$

By $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-(d_n)}$ denote any number $x \in [0, 1]$ having expansion (3). This notation is called *the nega- (d_n) -representation of $x \in [0, 1]$* . The number d_n in (3) is called *the n th element* and $\varepsilon_n = \varepsilon_n(x)$ is *the n th digit* of expansion (3).

2. Some Properties

Suppose that $x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1(x) \varepsilon_2(x) \dots \varepsilon_n(x) \dots}^{-D}$ and $y = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1(y) \varepsilon_2(y) \dots \varepsilon_n(y) \dots}^{-D}$.

Proposition 1. *The inequality $x < y$ holds for any numbers x and y from $[-1 + a_0, a_0]$ if and only if there exists a number m such that*

$$\varepsilon_n(x) = \varepsilon_n(y) \text{ for } n < 2m \text{ and } \varepsilon_{2m}(x) < \varepsilon_{2m}(y)$$

or

$$\varepsilon_n(x) = \varepsilon_n(y) \text{ for } n < 2m - 1 \text{ and } \varepsilon_{2m-1}(x) > \varepsilon_{2m-1}(y).$$

Proposition 2. *Suppose that $x_1 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{2k-1}}^{-D}(0)$, $x_2 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{2k}}^{-D}(0)$, and $x_3 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{2k+1}}^{-D}(0)$, and $\varepsilon_i \neq 0$ for all $i = 1, 2k+1$. Then the following two-sided inequality holds:*

$$x_1 < x_3 < x_2.$$

Proof. This statement follows from the relationship

$$x_3 = x_1 + \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2k}} \left(\varepsilon_{2k} - \frac{\varepsilon_{2k+1}}{d_{2k+1}} \right) = x_2 - \frac{\varepsilon_{2k+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2k+1}}.$$

□

Proposition 3. *Suppose that $z_1 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{2k}}^{-D}(0)$, $z_2 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{2k+1}}^{-D}(0)$, and $z_3 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{2k+2}}^{-D}(0)$, and $\varepsilon_i \neq 0$ for all $i = 1, 2k+2$. Then the two-sided inequality*

$$z_2 < z_3 < z_1$$

holds.

Proof. Since the relationship

$$z_3 = z_1 - \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2k+1}} \left(\varepsilon_{2k+1} - \frac{\varepsilon_{2k+2}}{d_{2k+2}} \right) = z_2 + \frac{\varepsilon_{2k+2}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2k+2}}$$

holds, we see that our statement is true.

□

3. Relations Between Positive and Alternating Cantor Series

Let (d_n) be a fixed sequence of positive integers, $d_n > 1$. For any $x \in [0, 1]$ there exists a sequence (α_n) , where $\alpha_n \in A_{d_n}$, such that

$$\Delta_{\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n \dots}^D = x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n}.$$

It is obvious that

$$x = \frac{\alpha_1 d_2 + \alpha_2}{d_1 d_2} + \frac{\alpha_3 d_4 + \alpha_4}{d_1 d_2 d_3 d_4} + \dots + \frac{\alpha_{2n-1} d_{2n} + \alpha_{2n}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2n}} + \dots$$

This representation is the representation of x by a positive Cantor series with the sequence of elements (d'_n) , where $d'_n = d_{2n-1} d_{2n}$. In fact, $0 \leq \alpha_{2n-1} d_{2n} + \alpha_{2n} \leq d_{2n-1} d_{2n} - 1$ and therefore,

$$\Delta_{\beta_1 \beta_2 \dots \beta_n \dots}^{D'} = x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\beta_n}{p_1 p_2 \dots p_n}, \tag{4}$$

where $\beta_n = \alpha_{2n-1}d_{2n} + \alpha_{2n}$, $p_n = d_{2n-1}d_{2n}$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Let us consider representation (2). Using the same technique, we get

$$x = \frac{\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1 d_2}{d_1 d_2} + \frac{\varepsilon_4 - \varepsilon_3 d_4}{d_1 d_2 d_3 d_4} + \dots + \frac{\varepsilon_{2n} - \varepsilon_{2n-1} d_{2n}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2n}} + \dots$$

But $(\varepsilon_{2n} - \varepsilon_{2n-1} d_{2n})$ belongs to $\{0, 1, \dots, d_{2n-1}d_{2n} - 1\}$ for not all values of ε_{2n-1} and ε_{2n} .

Consider expansion (3). Indeed, for

$$\Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n}^{-(d_n)} = x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 + \delta_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} (-1)^{n+1},$$

where

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \equiv \Delta_{0[d_2-1]0[d_4-1]0\dots}^{-D},$$

we obtain

$$x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2n} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2n}} + \frac{\delta_1 d_2 - \delta_2}{d_1 d_2} + \frac{\delta_3 d_4 - \delta_4}{d_1 d_2 d_3 d_4} + \dots + \frac{\delta_{2n-1} d_{2n} - \delta_{2n}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2n}} + \dots$$

Thus the number $(\delta_{2n-1} d_{2n} - \delta_{2n} + d_{2n} - 1)$ always belongs to $\{0, 1, \dots, d_{2n-1}d_{2n} - 1\}$ for any nega- (d_n) -representation and

$$\Delta_{\gamma_1 \gamma_2 \dots \gamma_n}^{D'} = x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(\delta_{2n-1} + 1)d_{2n} - \delta_{2n} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{2n}}, \tag{5}$$

where $\gamma_n = (\delta_{2n-1} + 1)d_{2n} - \delta_{2n} - 1 = \delta_{2n-1}d_{2n} + d_{2n} - 1 - \delta_{2n}$.

The next statement follows from (4) and (5).

Lemma 5. *The following functions are identity transformations:*

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n}^D \xrightarrow{f} \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 [d_2-1-\varepsilon_2] \dots \varepsilon_{2n-1} [d_{2n-1}-\varepsilon_{2n}] \dots}^{-(d_n)} = f(x) = y, \\ x &= \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n}^{-(d_n)} \xrightarrow{g} \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 [d_2-1-\varepsilon_2] \dots \varepsilon_{2n-1} [d_{2n-1}-\varepsilon_{2n}] \dots}^D = g(x) = y. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the following functions are DP-functions (functions preserving the fractal Hausdorff-Besicovitch dimension):

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n}^D \xrightarrow{f} \Delta_{[d_1-1-\varepsilon_1] \varepsilon_2 \dots [d_{2n-1}-1-\varepsilon_{2n-1}] \varepsilon_{2n} \dots}^{-(d_n)} = f(x) = y, \\ x &= \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n}^{-(d_n)} \xrightarrow{g} \Delta_{[d_1-1-\varepsilon_1] \varepsilon_2 \dots [d_{2n-1}-1-\varepsilon_{2n-1}] \varepsilon_{2n} \dots}^D = g(x) = y. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 6. *The following relationships are true:*

1. $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^D - \Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D} = 2\Delta_{\varepsilon_10\varepsilon_30\dots}^D = -2\Delta_{\varepsilon_10\varepsilon_30\dots}^{-D};$
2. $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^D + \Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D} = 2\Delta_{0\varepsilon_20\varepsilon_4\dots}^D = 2\Delta_{0\varepsilon_20\varepsilon_4\dots}^{-D};$
3. $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^D - \Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-(d_n)} = 2\Delta_{\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_4\varepsilon_6\dots}^{D'} - \Delta_{[d_2-1][d_4-1]\dots}^{D'}, \varepsilon_n \in A_{d_n};$
4. $\Delta_{\gamma_1\gamma_2\dots\gamma_n\dots}^{D'} = \Delta_{\beta_1\beta_2\dots\beta_n\dots}^{D'} + \Delta_{[d_2-1][d_4-1]\dots[d_{2n}-1]\dots}^{D'} - 2\Delta_{\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_4\varepsilon_6\dots}^{D'}.$

4. Shift Operators

Let $\mathcal{F}_{[-1+a_0, a_0]}^{-D}$ be the set of all nega-D-expansions of real numbers from $[-1 + a_0, a_0]$.

Define the shift operator $\hat{\varphi}$ of expansion (2) on $\mathcal{F}_{[-1+a_0, a_0]}^{-D}$ by the rule

$$\hat{\varphi} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} \varepsilon_n}{d_2 d_3 \cdots d_n}.$$

In other words,

$$\hat{\varphi}(\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D}) = \Delta_{\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D_1} = -d_1 \Delta_{0\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D}.$$

This operator generates some function $\hat{\varphi}$ such that

$$\hat{\varphi} : [-1 + a_0, a_0] \rightarrow [-a_0 d_1, 1 - a_0 d_1].$$

By definition, put

$$\hat{\varphi}^k \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \right) = \sum_{n=k+1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-k} \varepsilon_n}{d_{k+1} \cdots d_n},$$

$$\hat{\varphi}^k(\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D}) = \Delta_{\varepsilon_{k+1}\varepsilon_{k+2}\dots}^{-D_k} = (-1)^k d_1 d_2 \cdots d_k \Delta_{\underbrace{0\dots 0}_k \varepsilon_{k+1}\varepsilon_{k+2}\dots}^{-D}.$$

Define the generalized shift operator $\hat{\varphi}_m$ of expansion (2) by the rule

$$\hat{\varphi}_m \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n} \right) = -\frac{\varepsilon_1}{d_1} + \cdots + \frac{(-1)^{m-1} \varepsilon_{m-1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{m-1}} + \frac{(-1)^m \varepsilon_{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{m-1} d_{m+1}} + \cdots,$$

i.e.,

$$\hat{\varphi}_m(\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_{m-1}\varepsilon_m\varepsilon_{m+1}\dots}^{-D}) = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_{m-1}\varepsilon_{m+1}\dots}^{-D_m}.$$

Remark 3. Since (ε_n) and (d_n) are fixed sequences in (2) for a given $x \in [a_0 - 1, a_0]$, we see that the operator $\hat{\varphi}$ or $\hat{\varphi}_m$ takes each number to a number represented in terms of the “other” numeral system.

It is easy to see that the operator $\hat{\varphi}$ has exactly d_1 invariant points. These are points of the form

$$-\frac{i}{d_1 + 1}, \quad i = \overline{0, d_1 - 1}.$$

The operator $\hat{\varphi}$ is not a bijection because the points $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$ ($\varepsilon_1 = \overline{0, d_1 - 1}$) are preimages of the point $\Delta_{\varepsilon_2 \varepsilon_3 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D_1}$.

If a sequence (d_n) is purely periodic with a period of length k , then the mapping $\hat{\varphi}$ has periodic points with a period of length k , $k \in \mathbb{N}$, i.e.,

$$\hat{\varphi}^{k+t}(\Delta_{(\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_k)}^{-D}) = \hat{\varphi}^{kt+t}(\Delta_{(\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_k)}^{-D}), \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Lemma 7. *If a sequence (d_n) is purely periodic with a simple period, then the following set*

$$C[-D, V] = \{x : x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}, \varepsilon_n \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m\} \subset \{0, 1, \dots, d_n - 1\}\}$$

is an invariant set under the mapping $\hat{\varphi}$. Here v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m are fixed positive integers, $1 < m \leq d_n - 1$, and $d_n > 2$.

Lemma 8. *If sequences (d_n) and (V_n) are purely periodic with a period of length k , then the set*

$$C[-D, V_n] = \{x : x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}, \varepsilon_n \in V_n = \{v_1^{(n)}, v_2^{(n)}, \dots, v_m^{(n)}\} \subset A_{d_n}\}$$

is an invariant set under the mapping $\hat{\varphi}^k$.

Define the shift operator $\tilde{\varphi}$ of the nega- D -representation of x by the rule

$$\tilde{\varphi}(x) = \tilde{\varphi}(\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}) = \Delta_{\varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_{n+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n}.$$

It is obvious that the mapping $\tilde{\varphi}$ is not always well-defined. In fact, the inequality $\varepsilon_{n+1} \leq d_n - 1$ holds for not all alternating Cantor series. The next statement follows from the last-mentioned inequality.

Lemma 9. *The operator $\tilde{\varphi}$ is well-defined if and only if the inequality*

$$d_{n+1} \leq d_n$$

holds for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Remark 4. In Lemma 9, we understand that $\tilde{\varphi}$ is well-defined in the wide sense, i.e., for each $x \in [a_0 - 1, a_0]$. In fact, for any sequence (d_n) there exist points from $[a_0 - 1, a_0]$ such that the function $\tilde{\varphi}$ is well-defined at these points.

Lemma 10. *If there exists a number $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\hat{\varphi}^m(x) = x$, then*

$$x = \left(1 + \frac{1}{(-1)^m d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m - 1}\right) \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m}^{-D}.$$

Proof. Let $x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n}^{-D}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m \varepsilon_{m+1} \dots}^{-D} = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m}^{-D} + \underbrace{\Delta_{\underbrace{0 \dots 0}_m}_{\varepsilon_{m+1} \varepsilon_{m+2} \dots}}^{-D} \\ &= \varphi^m(x) = (-1)^m d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m \underbrace{\Delta_{\underbrace{0 \dots 0}_m}_{\varepsilon_{m+1} \varepsilon_{m+2} \dots}}^D. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof. □

Lemma 11. *Let x be a fixed number. If there exist $m \in \mathbb{Z}_0$ and $c \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\hat{\varphi}^m(x) = \hat{\varphi}^{m+c}(x)$, then*

$$x = \frac{\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m}^{-D} + (-1)^{c+1} d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+c} \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m+c}}^{-D}}{1 + (-1)^{c+1} d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+c}}.$$

Proof. The statement follows from the next equality:

$$x - \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_m}^{-D} = (-1)^c d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+c} (x - \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m+c}}^{-D}).$$

□

Lemma 12. *The equalities*

$$\hat{\varphi}^k(x) = (-1)^k d_1 d_2 \cdots d_k x + (-1)^{k+1} d_1 d_2 \cdots d_k \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_k}^{-D}$$

and

$$x = (-1)^k \frac{\hat{\varphi}^k(x) + (-1)^k d_1 d_2 \cdots d_k \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_k}^{-D}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_k}$$

hold for an arbitrary $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

The next proposition follows from the last-mentioned lemma.

Lemma 13. *The equality*

$$\begin{aligned} &(-1)^c d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+c} \cdot \hat{\varphi}^m(x) - \hat{\varphi}^{m+c}(x) \\ &= (-1)^{m+c} d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{m+c} \cdot \underbrace{\Delta_{\underbrace{0 \dots 0}_m}_{\varepsilon_{m+1} \varepsilon_{m+2} \dots \varepsilon_{m+c}}^{-D}} \end{aligned}$$

holds for arbitrary numbers $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $c \in \mathbb{N}$.

Theorem 2. *The mapping $\hat{\varphi}$ is decreasing on each first rank interval $\nabla_c^{-D} = (\inf \Delta_c^{-D}, \sup \Delta_c^{-D})$.*

Proof. Let points $x_1 = \Delta_{c\varepsilon_2(x_1)\varepsilon_3(x_1)\dots\varepsilon_n(x_1)\dots}^{-D}$ and $x_2 = \Delta_{c\varepsilon_2(x_2)\varepsilon_3(x_2)\dots\varepsilon_n(x_2)\dots}^{-D}$ ($x_1 < x_2$) be arbitrary points from the interval ∇_c^{-D} .

Since the equality $\varepsilon_n(\hat{\varphi}(x)) = \varepsilon_{n+1}(x)$ holds and Proposition 1 is true for x_1 and x_2 , we see that the inequality $\hat{\varphi}(x_1) > \hat{\varphi}(x_2)$ holds. \square

The next statement follows from this theorem.

Corollary 1. *The mapping $\hat{\varphi}$ has a derivative almost everywhere (with respect to the Lebesgue measure).*

Theorem 3. *The mapping $\hat{\varphi}$ is continuous at each point of the first rank interval ∇_c^{-D} and the endpoints of this interval are points of discontinuity of the mapping.*

Proof. Let $x = \Delta_{c\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D}$ be an arbitrary nega-D-irrational point from ∇_c^{-D} . Let (x_m) be an arbitrary sequence of points from ∇_c^{-D} such that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} x_m = x$. Then

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} x_m = x \Leftrightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n_m = \infty,$$

where $n_m = \min\{n : \varepsilon_n(x_m) \neq \varepsilon_n(x)\}$. The last-mentioned equivalence follows from the definition and basic properties of the nega-D-representation.

Since $\varepsilon_n(\hat{\varphi}(x)) = \varepsilon_{n+1}(x)$ holds, we have $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\varphi}(x_m) = \hat{\varphi}(x)$. Therefore the mapping $\hat{\varphi}$ is continuous at the point x .

Let x_0 be a certain nega-D-rational point from ∇_c^{-D} , i.e.,

$$x_0 = \Delta_{c\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3\dots\varepsilon_n[d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0\dots}^{-D} = \Delta_{c\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3\dots\varepsilon_{n-1}[\varepsilon_n-1]0[d_{n+2}-1]0[d_{n+4}-1]0\dots}^{-D}.$$

At the same time

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \hat{\varphi}(x) = \Delta_{\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n[d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0\dots}^{-D_1} = \Delta_{\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_{n-1}[\varepsilon_n-1]0[d_{n+2}-1]0[d_{n+4}-1]0\dots}^{-D_1}.$$

Indeed, the existence of the left-hand and right-hand finite limits at each point follows from monotonicity and boundedness of the mapping.

Consider the problem of continuity of $\hat{\varphi}$ at the point

$$x_1 = \Delta_{c[d_2-1]0[d_4-1]0\dots}^{-D} = \Delta_{[c-1]0[d_3-1]0[d_5-1]0\dots}^{-D} = x_2, \quad c \neq 0.$$

The endpoints of the interval ∇_c^{-D} are the jump points of $\hat{\varphi}$ because

$$\hat{\varphi}(x_1) = \Delta_{[d_2-1]0[d_4-1]0\dots}^{-D_1} \neq \Delta_{0[d_3-1]0[d_5-1]0\dots}^{-D_1} = \hat{\varphi}(x_2).$$

\square

Theorem 4. *If the mapping $\hat{\varphi}$ has a derivative at the point $x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D}$, then*

$$(\hat{\varphi}(x))' = -d_1.$$

Proof. Suppose that $\hat{\varphi}$ has a derivative at the point x_0 . Let (x_n) be a sequence of $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1(x_0)\varepsilon_2(x_0)\dots\varepsilon_n(x_0)\varepsilon_{n+1}(x_0)\dots}^{-D}$. Here $\varepsilon_k(x) \neq \varepsilon_k(x_0)$ for all $k > n$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\hat{\varphi}(x))' &= \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\hat{\varphi}(x) - \hat{\varphi}(x_0)}{x - x_0} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta_{\varepsilon_2(x)\varepsilon_3(x)\dots}^{-D} - \Delta_{\varepsilon_2(x_0)\varepsilon_3(x_0)\dots}^{-D}}{\Delta x} \\ &= - \lim_{\varepsilon_n(x) \rightarrow \varepsilon_n(x_0)} \frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i(x)}{d_2 \dots d_i} - \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i(x_0)}{d_2 \dots d_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j(x)}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j(x_0)}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j}} \\ &= - \lim_{\varepsilon_n(x) \rightarrow \varepsilon_n(x_0)} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j(x)}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j(x_0)}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} + \frac{\varepsilon_1(x) - \varepsilon_1(x_0)}{d_1}}{\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j(x)}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j(x_0)}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j}} d_1 = -d_1. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2. *The derivative of $\hat{\varphi}^k$ does not exist at an arbitrary nega- D -rational point $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_{n-1}\varepsilon_n[d_{n+1}-1]0[d_{n+3}-1]0\dots}^{-D}$ when $k > n - 1$.*

5. Representations of Rational and Irrational Numbers

The main statements of this section are analogous to the main results of the paper [8].

Theorem 5. *A rational number $x = \frac{p}{q}$ from $[-1 + a_0, a_0]$ has a finite expansion by series (2) if and only if there exists a number n_0 such that $d_1 d_2 \dots d_{n_0} \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$.*

Corollary 3. *There exist sequences (d_n) such that every rational number has the finite nega- D -expansion. Consider the following examples:*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{2 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot (n+1)}, \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot \dots \cdot 2n}.$$

Lemma 14. *The equality*

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-(d_n)} + \Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n\dots}^{-D} + \Delta_{(1)}^{-D} = 0$$

holds for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Corollary 4. *There exist alternating Cantor series (3) such that a number of the form $\Delta_{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2\dots\varepsilon_n(0)}^{-(d_n)}$ is an irrational number.*

The following propositions are equivalent.

Theorem 6. *A number $x_0 \in [-1 + a_0, a_0]$ is a rational number if and only if there exist $k \in \mathbb{Z}_0$ and $t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that*

$$\hat{\varphi}^k(x) = \hat{\varphi}^t(x).$$

Theorem 7. A number $x_0 \in [-1 + a_0, a_0]$ is a rational number if and only if there exist $k \in \mathbb{Z}_0$ and $t \in \mathbb{N}$ ($k < t$) such that

$$\Delta_{\underbrace{0 \dots 0}_k \varepsilon_{k+1} \varepsilon_{k+2} \varepsilon_{k+3} \dots}^{-D} = (-1)^{t-k} d_{k+1} d_{k+2} \dots d_t \Delta_{\underbrace{0 \dots 0}_t \varepsilon_{t+1} \varepsilon_{t+2} \varepsilon_{t+3} \dots}^{-D}.$$

Theorem 8. A number x is a rational number if and only if the sequence $(\hat{\varphi}^k(x))$, where $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, contains at least two identical terms.

6. Foundations of the Metric Theory

Let (d_n) be a fixed sequence of positive integers, $d_n > 1$. Let c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m be an ordered tuple of integers such that $c_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, d_i - 1\}$ for $i = \overline{1, m}$.

Definition 5. A *nega-D-cylinder of rank m with base $c_1 c_2 \dots c_m$* is a set $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}$ formed by all numbers of the segment $[-1 + a_0, a_0]$ with nega-D-representations in which the first m digits coincide with c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m , respectively, i.e.,

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = \{x : x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}, \varepsilon_j = c_j, j = \overline{1, m}\}.$$

Lemma 15. A *nega-D-cylinder is a closed interval, i.e.,*

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = \begin{cases} \left[g_m + \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} (a_m - 1), g_m + \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} a_m \right] & \text{if } m \text{ is even} \\ \left[g_m + \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} a_m, g_m + \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} (a_m - 1) \right] & \text{if } m \text{ is odd,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$a_m = \sup \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_{m+j}}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \dots d_{m+j}}, \quad g_m = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{(-1)^i c_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i}.$$

Proof. Let m be even and $x \in \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}$, i.e.,

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{(-1)^i c_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_j}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j},$$

where $\varepsilon_j \in \{0, 1, \dots, d_j - 1\}$; then

$$x' = g_m - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2k-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+2k-1}} \leq x \leq g_m + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2k} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+2k}} = x''.$$

Hence $x \in [x', x'']$ and $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} \subseteq [x', x'']$.

Since the equalities

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2j} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{m+2j}} = \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m} \sup \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_{m+j}}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+j}}$$

and

$$-\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2j-1} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{m+2j-1}} = \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m} \inf \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_{m+j}}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+j}}$$

hold, we have $x \in \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}$ and $x', x'' \in \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}$. □

Lemma 16. *Nega-D-cylinders have the following properties:*

1.

$$\inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = \begin{cases} g_m - \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2j-1} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+2j-1}} & \text{if } m \text{ is even} \\ g_m - \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2j} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+2j}} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

2.

$$\sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = \begin{cases} g_m + \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2j} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+2j}} & \text{if } m \text{ is even} \\ g_m + \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{m+2j-1} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} \cdots d_{m+2j-1}} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

3.

$$|\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}| = \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_m}.$$

4.

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} \subset \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}.$$

5.

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = \bigcup_{c=0}^{d_{m+1}-1} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D}.$$

6.

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} |\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}| = 0.$$

7.

$$\frac{|\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c_{m+1}}^{-D}|}{|\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}|} = \frac{1}{d_{m+1}}.$$

$$8. \quad \begin{cases} \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} = \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m [c+1]}^{-D} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd} \\ \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m [c+1]}^{-D} = \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} & \text{if } m \text{ is even,} \end{cases}$$

where $c \neq d_{m+1} - 1$.

$$9. \quad \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} \cap \Delta_{e_1 e_2 \dots e_m}^{-D} = \begin{cases} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} & \text{if } e_i = c_i \text{ for } i = \overline{1, m} \\ \emptyset & \text{if } \exists i (i < m) \text{ such that } c_i \neq e_i \\ \emptyset & \text{if } \exists i \text{ such that } c_i \neq e_i, c_m \neq e_m - 1. \end{cases}$$

Here $e_m \neq 0$ in the last case.

$$10. \quad \bigcap_{m=1}^{\infty} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = x = \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m \dots}^{-D}.$$

Proof. Properties 1 and 2 follow immediately from the definition of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}$. Property 3 is a corollary of these properties. Properties 6 and 7 follow from Property 3.

Property 4. Let m be even. Let us prove that the conditions

$$\begin{cases} \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} \geq \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} \\ \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} \leq \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} \end{cases}$$

hold. In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} & \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} - \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D} = g_m + \frac{(-1)^{m+1} c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} \\ & + \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} \left(\frac{d_{m+3} - 1}{d_{m+2} d_{m+3}} + \frac{d_{m+5} - 1}{d_{m+2} \dots d_{m+5}} + \dots \right) - g_m \\ & - \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} \left(-\frac{d_{m+1} - 1}{d_{m+1}} - \frac{d_{m+3} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2} d_{m+3}} - \frac{d_{m+5} - 1}{d_{m+1} \dots d_{m+5}} - \dots \right) \\ & = \frac{d_{m+1} - 1 - c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

If the condition $c = d_{m+1} - 1$ holds, then the last inequality is an equality. As above,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup \Delta_{c_1 \dots c_m}^{-D} - \sup \Delta_{c_1 \dots c_m c}^{-D} = \frac{(-1)^m}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_m} \left(\frac{d_{m+2} - 1}{d_{m+1} d_{m+2}} + \frac{d_{m+4} - 1}{d_{m+1} \dots d_{m+4}} + \dots \right) \\ & + g_m - g_m - \frac{(-1)^{m+1} c}{d_1 \dots d_{m+1}} - \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 \dots d_{m+1}} \left(-\frac{d_{m+2} - 1}{d_{m+2}} - \frac{d_{m+4} - 1}{d_{m+2} \dots d_{m+4}} - \dots \right) \\ & = \frac{c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Here the last inequality is an equality whenever the condition $c = 0$ holds.

Similarly, the last-mentioned system of inequalities is true in the case of odd m .

Property 5 follows from *Property 4* and the definition of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{-D}$.

Property 8. Let m be odd. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} - \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m [c+1]}^{-D} &= \frac{(-1)^{m+1} c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} + \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} a_{m+1} \\ &- \frac{c+1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} (-1)^{m+1} - \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} (a_{m+1} - 1) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Let m be even. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m [c+1]}^{-D} - \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m c}^{-D} &= \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} (c+1) \\ &+ \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} (a_{m+1} - 1) - \frac{(-1)^{m+1} c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} - \frac{(-1)^{m+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{m+1}} a_{m+1} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Property 9 follows from *properties 1, 2, and 8*.

Property 10. From *Property 4* it follows that

$$\Delta_{c_1}^{-D} \subset \Delta_{c_1 c_2}^{-D} \subset \Delta_{c_1 c_2 c_3}^{-D} \subset \dots \subset \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} \subset \dots$$

Since the last lemma and Cantor's intersection theorem are true, we obtain

$$\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} = x = \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \dots}^{-D}$$

□

7. Simplest Metric Problems

Let k be a fixed positive integer, c be a fixed digit from A_{d_k} . Consider the following set

$$\Delta_c^k = \{x : x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{k-1} c \varepsilon_{k+1} \dots}^{-D}\}.$$

Lemma 17. *The set Δ_c^k ($k > 1$) is the union of nega- D -cylinders of rank k .*

Proof. Let $k = 1$. Then it is easy to see that $\Delta_c^k = \Delta_c^{-D}$.

Let $k = 2$. Then

$$\Delta_c^2 = \Delta_{0c}^{-D} \cup \Delta_{1c}^{-D} \cup \Delta_{2c}^{-D} \cup \dots \cup \Delta_{[d_1-1]c}^{-D}.$$

Let $k = n$. Then

$$\Delta_c^n = \underbrace{\Delta_{\underbrace{00 \dots 00}_{n-1} c}^{-D}} \cup \underbrace{\Delta_{\underbrace{00 \dots 01}_{n-1} c}^{-D}} \cup \dots \cup \Delta_{[d_1-1][d_2-1] \dots [d_{n-1}-1]c}^{-D}.$$

□

Lemma 18. *The Lebesgue measure of Δ_c^k is equal to $\frac{1}{d_k}$.*

Proof. It is easy to see that

$$\lambda(\Delta_c^k) = \sum_{c_1=0}^{d_1-1} \dots \sum_{c_{k-1}=0}^{d_{k-1}-1} |\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{k-1} c}^{-D}| = \frac{1}{d_k} \sum_{c_1=0}^{d_1-1} \dots \sum_{c_{k-1}=0}^{d_{k-1}-1} |\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{k-1}}^{-D}| = \frac{1}{d_k}.$$

□

Corollary 5. *The Lebesgue measure of $\Delta_{\varepsilon}^k = \{x : x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}, \varepsilon_k \neq c\}$ is equal to $1 - \frac{1}{d_k}$.*

Lemma 19. *The diameter of the set Δ_c^k is calculated by the following formula*

$$d(\Delta_c^k) = \frac{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k - d_k + 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k}.$$

Proof. Let k be even,

$$a_k = \sup \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \varepsilon_{k+j}}{d_{k+1} d_{k+2} \dots d_{k+j}}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} d(\Delta_c^k) &= \max \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \frac{(-1)^k c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} + \frac{(-1)^k}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} a_k \\ &\quad - \min \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^i \varepsilon_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} - \frac{(-1)^k c}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} - \frac{(-1)^k}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} (a_k - 1) \\ &= \left(\frac{d_2 - 1}{d_1 d_2} + \frac{d_4 - 1}{d_1 \dots d_4} + \dots + \frac{d_{k-2} - 1}{d_1 \dots d_{k-2}} \right) \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{d_1 - 1}{d_1} + \frac{d_3 - 1}{d_1 d_2 d_3} + \dots + \frac{d_{k-1} - 1}{d_1 \dots d_{k-1}} \right) + \frac{(-1)^k}{d_1 \dots d_k} \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{d_1 \dots d_{k-1}} + \frac{(-1)^k}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} = \frac{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k - d_k + 1}{d_1 \dots d_k}. \end{aligned}$$

Let k be odd. Then

$$\begin{aligned} d(\Delta_c^k) &= \left(\frac{d_2 - 1}{d_1 d_2} + \frac{d_4 - 1}{d_1 \dots d_4} + \dots + \frac{d_{k-1} - 1}{d_1 \dots d_{k-1}} \right) \\ &\quad - \left(-\frac{d_1 - 1}{d_1} - \frac{d_3 - 1}{d_1 d_2 d_3} - \dots - \frac{d_{k-2} - 1}{d_1 \dots d_{k-2}} \right) + \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k-1}} + \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} = \frac{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k - d_k + 1}{d_1 \dots d_k}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Let (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m) and (k_1, k_2, \dots, k_m) be fixed tuples of positive integers such that $c_i \in A_{d_{k_i}}$, $i = \overline{1, m}$, $0 < k_1 < k_2 < \dots < k_m$. Consider the following set

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m} = \{x : x = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \dots \varepsilon_{k_1-1} c_1 \varepsilon_{k_1+1} \dots \varepsilon_{k_2-1} c_2 \dots \varepsilon_{k_m-1} c_m \varepsilon_{k_m+1} \varepsilon_{k_m+2} \dots}\}.$$

Lemma 20. *The Lebesgue measure of the set $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}$ is calculated by the formula*

$$\lambda(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}) = \prod_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{d_{k_i}}.$$

Proof. It is easy to see that

$$\lambda(\Delta_{c_1 c_2}^{k_1 k_2}) = \frac{1}{d_{k_2}} \cdot \frac{d_{k_2-1}}{d_{k_2-1}} \cdot \dots \cdot \frac{d_{k_1+1}}{d_{k_1+1}} |\Delta_{c_1}^{k_1}| = \frac{1}{d_{k_2}} \cdot \frac{1}{d_{k_1}} = \lambda(\Delta_{c_1}^{k_1}) \cdot \lambda(\Delta_{c_2}^{k_2}).$$

Clearly,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}) &= \frac{1}{d_{k_m}} \left| \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{m-1}}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_{m-1}} \right| = \frac{1}{d_{k_m}} \cdot \frac{1}{d_{k_{m-1}}} \left| \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{m-2}}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_{m-2}} \right| = \dots \\ &= \frac{1}{d_{k_m}} \cdot \frac{1}{d_{k_{m-1}}} \cdot \dots \cdot \frac{1}{d_{k_1}} = \frac{1}{d_{k_1} d_{k_2} \dots d_{k_m}}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 6. *Sets of the form $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}$ are metrically independent, i.e.,*

$$\lambda(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}) = \lambda\left(\bigcap_{i=1}^m \Delta_{c_i}^{k_i}\right) = \prod_{i=1}^m \lambda(\Delta_{c_i}^{k_i}).$$

Lemma 21. *The diameter $d(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m})$ of the set $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}$ is calculated by the formula*

$$d(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m}) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{d_{k_i} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k_i}}.$$

Proof. Let $K = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_m\}$ and $l = 1, 2, \dots$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m} - \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{k_1 k_2 \dots k_m} \\ &= \sum_{2l=j \notin K, j < k_m} \frac{d_j - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} + \frac{(-1)^{k_m}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k_m}} \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{k_m+2p} - 1}{d_{k_m+1} \dots d_{k_m+2p}} \\ &+ \frac{(-1)^{k_m}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k_m}} \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{k_m+2p} - 1}{d_{k_m+1} \dots d_{k_m+2p}} \\ &- \sum_{2l+1=j \notin K, j < k_m} \frac{1 - d_j}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} - \frac{(-1)^{k_m}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k_m}} \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - d_{k_m+2p+1}}{d_{k_m+1} \dots d_{k_m+2p+1}} \\ &= \sum_{0 < j < k_m, j \notin K} \frac{d_j - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_j} + \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k_m}} = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{d_{k_i} - 1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{k_i}}. \end{aligned}$$

□

8. Alternating Cantor Series and the Hausdorff-Besicovitch Dimension Faithfulness

Let Φ_1 be the family of all closed intervals, Φ_2 be the family of all possible rank cylinders $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D}$, and E be an arbitrary subset of $[a_0 - 1, a_0]$.

Theorem 9. *If a sequence (d_n) is bounded, then the family Φ_2 of coverings of $[a_0 - 1, a_0]$ is faithful for the Hausdorff-Besicovitch dimension calculation.*

Proof. Let us find conditions for (d_n) such that the inequality

$$m_\varepsilon^\alpha(E, \Phi_1) \leq m_\varepsilon^\alpha(E, \Phi_2)$$

holds for $\Phi_2 \subset \Phi_1$.

Let u be an arbitrary closed interval of covering of E , k be the minimal positive integer such that u does not contain nega-D-cylinders $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{k-1}}^{-D}$ of rank $k - 1$. Then u belongs to not more than d_k cylinders of rank k but u contains a cylinder of rank $k + 1$. Hence,

$$m_\varepsilon^\alpha(E, \Phi_1) \leq m_\varepsilon^\alpha(E, \Phi_2) \leq d_k d_{k+1} m_\varepsilon^\alpha(E, \Phi_1),$$

where

$$m_\varepsilon^\alpha(E, \Phi) = \inf_{d(E_j) \leq \varepsilon} \sum_j d^\alpha(E_j)$$

for a fixed $\varepsilon > 0$, a fixed $\alpha > 0$, and covering of E by sets E_j with diameters $d(E_j) \leq \varepsilon$.

Note that $d_k d_{k+1} \leq (\max_n \{d_n\})^2 < \infty$ whenever (d_n) is bounded. Indeed,

$$0 < \lambda_1 = \frac{1}{\max_n \{d_n\}} \leq \frac{|\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n i}^{-D}|}{|\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D}|} = \frac{1}{d_{n+1}} \leq \frac{1}{2} = \lambda_2 < 1,$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are fixed numbers for an arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}$. It is true if and only if a sequence (d_n) is bounded. □

9. Sets of Incomplete Sums

Let (d_n) be a fixed sequence of positive integers, $d_n > 1$, and let (ε_n) be a fixed sequence of digits. Then we have a fixed number of the form

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D} = s_0 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n}. \tag{6}$$

Let (A'_n) be a sequence of $A'_n = \{0, \varepsilon_n\}$ and

$$L'_{s_0} = A'_1 \times A'_2 \times A'_n \times \dots = \{\delta : \delta = (\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_n, \dots), \delta_n \in A'_n\}.$$

Definition 6. A number of the form

$$s = s(\delta) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \delta_n}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_n}, \tag{7}$$

where $\delta = (\delta_n) \in L'_{s_0}$, is called an *incomplete sum of alternating Cantor series* (6).

By M_{s_0} denote the set of all incomplete sums of alternating Cantor series (6), i.e.,

$$M_{s_0} = \{x : x = \Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n \dots}^{-D}, (\delta_n) \in L'_{s_0}\}.$$

It is obvious that

$$M_{s_0} \subset \left[-\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{2k-1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}}, \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{2k}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}} \right] = I_0^{M_{s_0}} \text{ for } s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$$

and $M_{s_0} = \{0\}$ for $s_0 = 0$. Moreover,

$$\bigcup_{s_0} M_{s_0} = \left[-\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k-1}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k-1}}, \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{d_{2k}}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_{2k}} \right].$$

We begin with definitions.

Definition 7. A cylinder of rank m with base $c_1 c_2 \dots c_m$ is a set of the following form

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_m}^{M_{s_0}} = \left\{ x : x = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^i c_i}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_i} + \sum_{j=n+1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j \delta_j}{d_1 d_2 \cdots d_j} \right\},$$

where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are fixed numbers from A'_1, A'_2, \dots, A'_n , respectively, and $\delta_j \in A'_j$.

Definition 8. A cylindrical closed interval (interval) $I_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$ ($\nabla_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$) of rank n with base $c_1 c_2 \dots c_n$ is a closed interval (interval) whose endpoints coincide with endpoints of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$.

The following properties of cylindrical sets follow from Definition 7:

1.
$$\inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} = \begin{cases} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n 0 \varepsilon_{n+2} 0 \varepsilon_{n+4} \dots}^{-D} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \varepsilon_{n+1} 0 \varepsilon_{n+3} 0 \varepsilon_{n+5} \dots}^{-D} & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$
2.
$$\sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} = \begin{cases} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \varepsilon_{n+1} 0 \varepsilon_{n+3} 0 \varepsilon_{n+5} \dots}^{-D} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n 0 \varepsilon_{n+2} 0 \varepsilon_{n+4} \dots}^{-D} & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

3.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta_{\underbrace{0 \dots 0}_n \varepsilon_{n+1} \varepsilon_{n+2} \dots}^D = 0.$$

4. If $\varepsilon_{n+1} \neq 0$, then $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} = \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n 0}^{M_{s_0}} \cup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \varepsilon_{n+1}}^{M_{s_0}}$.

5.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} &\subset I_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} \subset \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D}, \\ M_{s_0} &\subset \bigcup_{c_i \in A'_i, i=\overline{1, n}} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} \subset \bigcup_{c_i \in A'_i, i=\overline{1, n}} I_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}. \end{aligned}$$

6.

$$\left| \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} \setminus (\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n 0}^{-D} \cup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \varepsilon_{n+1}}^{-D}) \right| = \begin{cases} \frac{d_{n+1}-2}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{n+1}} & \text{if } \varepsilon_{n+1} > 0 \\ \frac{d_{n+1}-1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{n+1}} & \text{if } \varepsilon_{n+1} = 0. \end{cases}$$

Here by $|\cdot|$ denote the length of an interval and by \setminus denote the difference of sets.

Lemma 22. Let $s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$ be a fixed number, (c_n) be an arbitrary fixed sequence from L'_{s_0} ; then the following are true:

1.

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} = \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \dots}^{-D}.$$

2.

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} = \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} \cap M_{s_0},$$

where

$$M_{s_0} = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\bigcup_{c_i \in A'_i, i=\overline{1, n}} \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} \right)$$

and $A'_i = \{0, \varepsilon_i\}$ for all positive integers i .

Proof. 1. Let $x = \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \dots}^{-D}$. From the definition of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$ it follows that $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \dots}^{-D} = x \in \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$. Therefore $x \in \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} I_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$. The first statement follows from Property 5 of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$.

2. Let $x \in M_{s_0}$. Then x belongs to a certain cylinder $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} \subset \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D}$. Let us consider the set $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} \cap M_{s_0}$. Numbers of the form $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n \delta_{n+1} \delta_{n+2} \dots \delta_{n+k} \dots}^{-D}$ where $\delta_{n+k} \in A'_{n+k}$, are elements of this set. Consequently,

$$\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}} \subset (\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} \cap M_{s_0}).$$

Also, if $x \in (\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{-D} \cap M_{s_0})$, then $x \in \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$. □

Theorem 10. *The set M_{s_0} of incomplete sums of alternating Cantor series (6) is:*

1. *the one-element set $\{0\}$ whenever $s_0 = 0$;*
2. *a finite set whenever the condition $\varepsilon_n \neq 0$ holds for a finite number of n in $s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$;*
3. *the segment $[-\frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{3}]$ whenever $d_n = \text{const} = 2$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s_0 = -\frac{1}{3}$;*
4. *a union of finite number of segments whenever there exists a finite number of m_i ($i = \overline{1, k_0}$, k_0 is a fixed number) that $d_{m_i} \neq 2$ and $s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{m_{k_0}}(1)}^{-D}$;*
5. *an uncountable, perfect, and nowhere dense set of zero Lebesgue measure whenever $s_0 \neq 0$ and $d_n > 2$ hold for an infinite number of n .*

Proof. Since an alternating Cantor series is the nega-binary sum

$$-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon_2}{2^2} - \frac{\varepsilon_3}{2^3} + \dots + \frac{(-1)^n \varepsilon_n}{2^n} + \dots,$$

where $\varepsilon_n \in \{0, 1\}$, whenever $d_n = \text{const} = 2$ and the set M_{s_0} is $C[-D, A'_n]$, we see that *statements 1-4* are true.

We now prove *statement 5* is true. Let the mapping $f : M_{s_0} \rightarrow C[E, V_n]$, where $V_n = A'_n$, be given by

$$x = \Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n \dots}^{-D} \xrightarrow{f} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2 + \delta_1)(2 + \delta_1 + \delta_2) \dots (2 + \delta_1 + \dots + \delta_n)} = \Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n \dots}^E = f(x) = y.$$

Here $\Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n \dots}^E$ is the representation by an Engel series. This mapping is not a bijection at the nega-D-rational points

$$\Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_{k-1} \delta_k [d_{k+1}-1] 0 [d_{k+3}-1] 0 \dots}^{-D} = \Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_{k-1} [\delta_k-1] 0 [d_{k+2}-1] 0 [d_{k+4}-1] \dots}^{-D}$$

It is true when $s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{k-1} 1 [d_{k+1}-1] [d_{k+2}-1] [d_{k+3}-1] \dots}^{-D}$.

Since the set of nega-D-rational numbers is not more than countable in M_{s_0} , we can use one of the representations of a nega-D-rational number (e.g., the first representation) when the argument is a nega-D-rational number. Hence M_{s_0} is uncountable, since $C[E, V_n]$ is uncountable.

Let us prove that the set M_{s_0} is nowhere dense. Choose a cylinder $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1}}^{M_{s_0}}$ such that the condition $\varepsilon_n \neq 0$ holds for $s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_n \dots}^{-D}$. Consider the mutual

placement of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} 0}^{M_{s_0}}$ and $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} \varepsilon_n}^{M_{s_0}}$. Let n be even. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} \varepsilon_n}^{M_{s_0}} - \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} 0}^{M_{s_0}} &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^i c_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} + \frac{\varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \\ &- \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{n+2k-1}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{n+2k-1}} - \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^i c_i}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_i} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{n+2k}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{n+2k}} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_n}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{n+k}}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_{n+k}} = \frac{1}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_n} \left(\varepsilon_n - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{n+k}}{d_{n+1} \dots d_{n+k}} \right) \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

That is the cylinders are left-to-right situated and the last-mentioned difference equals zero when $s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} 1 [d_{n+1}-1] [d_{n+2}-1] [d_{n+3}-1] \dots}^{-D}$. Similarly, the inequality

$$\inf \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} 0}^{M_{s_0}} - \sup \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} \varepsilon_n}^{M_{s_0}} \geq 0$$

holds when n is odd. That is cylinders $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$ are right-to-left situated. Thus for any interval belonging to $[\inf M_{s_0}, \sup M_{s_0}]$ there exists a subinterval that does not contain points from M_{s_0} , since $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} 0}^{M_{s_0}} \cap \Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_{n-1} \varepsilon_n}^{M_{s_0}} \neq \emptyset$ if and only if

$$\varepsilon_n = 0 \text{ or } s_0 = \Delta_{\varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 \dots \varepsilon_{n-1} 1 [d_{n+1}-1] [d_{n+2}-1] [d_{n+3}-1] \dots}^{-D}.$$

Let us prove that M_{s_0} is a closed set without isolated points. Choose an arbitrary limit point x_0 from M_{s_0} . From the definition of a limit point it follows that for all $\varepsilon > 0$ an interval $(x_0 - \varepsilon, x_0 + \varepsilon)$ contains at least one point (that does not coincide with x_0) from M_{s_0} . If there does not exist a unique closed interval $I_{\delta_1(x_0) \delta_2(x_0) \dots \delta_n(x_0)}^{M_{s_0}}$ such that $x_0 \in I_{\delta_1(x_0) \delta_2(x_0) \dots \delta_n(x_0)}^{M_{s_0}}$, then x_0 belongs to one of the adjacent to M_{s_0} intervals. Therefore there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that $(x_0 - \varepsilon_0, x_0 + \varepsilon_0) \cap M_{s_0} = \emptyset$. In this case, x_0 is not a limit point. If there exists a closed interval $I_{\delta_1(x_0) \delta_2(x_0) \dots \delta_n(x_0)}^{M_{s_0}}$, then

$$x_0 = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} I_{\delta_1(x_0) \delta_2(x_0) \dots \delta_n(x_0)}^{M_{s_0}} \text{ and } x_0 \in M_{s_0}.$$

Hence M_{s_0} is a closed set.

Suppose there exists a certain isolated point $x' = \Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n \dots}^{-D}$. Then there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that

$$(x' - \varepsilon_0, x' + \varepsilon_0) \cap (M_{s_0} \setminus \{x'\}) = \emptyset. \tag{8}$$

Take a number m such that $d(\Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_m}^{M_{s_0}}) < \varepsilon_0$ and $\varepsilon_{m+1}(s_0) \neq 0$. Then $\Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_m}^{M_{s_0}} \subset (x' - \varepsilon_0, x' + \varepsilon_0)$ and

$$x' \neq x = \Delta_{\delta_1 \delta_2 \dots \delta_n \sigma \delta_{m+2} \dots}^{-D} \in (x' - \varepsilon_0, x' + \varepsilon_0) \cap M_{s_0},$$

where

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} \varepsilon_{m+1} & \text{if } \delta_{m+1} = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \delta_{m+1} \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

The last condition contradicts (8). The set M_{s_0} does not contain isolated points.

Let us calculate the Lebesgue measure of M_{s_0} . Let F_k be the union of closed intervals $I_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_k}^{M_{s_0}}$ of rank k ($c_k \in A'_k$). Then $M_{s_0} \subset F_k \subset F_{k+1}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\lambda(M_{s_0}) \leq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} F_k$. Since the condition $d(\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}) = |I_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}|$ and the properties of $\Delta_{c_1 c_2 \dots c_n}^{M_{s_0}}$ hold, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(M_{s_0}) &\leq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left(2^k \cdot \underbrace{\Delta_0^D \dots 0}_{k} \varepsilon_{k+1}(s_0) \varepsilon_{k+2}(s_0) \varepsilon_{k+3}(s_0) \dots \right) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2^k}{d_1 d_2 \dots d_k} \cdot \sum_{i=k+1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon_i(s_0)}{d_{k+1} \dots d_i} \right) = 0. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

References

[1] G. Cantor, Ueber die einfachen Zahlensysteme, *Z. Math. Phys.* **14** (1869), 121-128.

[2] K. Falconer, *Techniques in Fractal Geometry*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., Chichester, 1997.

[3] K. Falconer, *Fractal Geometry. Mathematical Foundations and Applications. Second edition*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, NJ, 2003.

[4] J. Galambos, *Representations of Real Numbers by Infinite Series*, Lecture Notes in Mathematics 502, Springer, 1976.

[5] S. Ito and T. Sadahiro, Beta-expansions with negative bases, *Integers* **9** (2009), 239-259.

[6] S. Kalpazidou, A. Knopfmacher and J. Knopfmacher, Metric properties of alternating Lüroth series, *Port. Math.* **48** (1991), no. 3, 319-325.

[7] B. Mance, *Normal Numbers with Respect to the Cantor Series Expansion*, Dissertation, The Ohio State University, 2010.

[8] S. Serbenyuk, Cantor series and rational numbers, available at <https://arxiv.org/abs/1702.00471>

[9] S. O. Serbenyuk, On some sets of real numbers such that defined by nega-s-adic and Cantor nega-s-adic representations, *Trans. Natl. Pedagog. Mykhailo Dragomanov Univ. Ser. 1. Phys. Math.* **15** (2013), 168-187, available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292970280> (in Ukrainian)

[10] S. O. Serbenyuk, Real numbers representation by the Cantor series, *International Conference on Algebra dedicated to 100th anniversary of S.M. Chernikov: Abstracts*, Dragomanov National Pedagogical University, Kyiv, 2012. - P. 136, available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/301849984>

[11] S. Serbenyuk, Nega- \tilde{Q} -representation as a generalization of certain alternating representations of real numbers, *Bull. Taras Shevchenko Natl. Univ. Kyiv Math. Mech.* **1 (35)** (2016), 32-39, available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308273000> (in Ukrainian)